

**3rd International
Radiocarbon
in the Environment
Conference**

5-9 July 2021, Gliwice, Poland

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Comparative dating of charcoal, tooth and ceramic samples from the Polutepe archaeological site in Azerbaijan

Aybaniz Ahadova, Sahib Mammadov

Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences, Institute of Radiation Problems

The radiocarbon dating method was used to date the age of a charcoal sample from the Polutepe archaeological site in the Jalilabad district of Azerbaijan. Polutepe is the largest Neolithic-Eneolithic monument in the Caucasus. A charcoal sample excavated at the Polutepe site was dated by the conventional radiocarbon method at 4270 ± 160 BC, which agrees with the stratigraphic estimated dates. ESR method has also been applied to determine the age of tooth enamel found in Polutepe archaeological site. The investigated object was presumably the lower jaw of a cow with well-preserved tooth. The mean age of the sample was determined as 5420 ± 130 BC years. The age of fragments of the ancient pottery sample from the same archaeological site has been estimated by employing Thermoluminescence dating method. The age of the sample was calculated by an additive dose method as 4360 ± 530 BC years which are in line with the charcoal samples.

Radiocarbon dating was performed using the conventional benzene synthesis method as described by Tamers. The assumption in carbon-14 dating is that the analyzed sample has undergone only radioactive decay within the years since it ceased interaction with the biosphere. However, the archaeological artifacts and geological specimens are usually found embedded in or contaminated by other carbon-containing materials, which affect the carbon-14 content of samples. The reliability of the dating of old charcoal samples depends on the chemical treatment of the sample to remove any external ^{14}C while leaving reliable fractions for dating. Charcoal samples of 25 grams were treated by an acid-alkali-acid (AAA) pretreatment method after removal of visible contaminants. The concentration of the acid (HCl) and alkali (NaOH) was 0.5%. In order to remove possible ammonia compounds, acetylene was passed through phosphoric acid. A chromium activated alumina-silica catalyst was used for conversion of acetylene to benzene at room temperature. Benzene was then evaporated out of the catalyst at 120°C and collected in a vacuum at liquid nitrogen temperature. The synthesized benzene was transferred into 20 ml low-potassium glass counting vials and increased to 3 ml volume by adding petroleum-derived benzene. As a scintillation solution, 1 ml of commercially available SIGMA-ALDRICH liquid scintillation mixture PPO/POPOP in toluene was added. The information needed for radiocarbon measurement performed by decay counting is the measured specific activity of the sample, a standard, and a background sample. As a background, commercially available petroleum-derived (i.e. dead) benzene was used. The ^{13}C isotopic fractionation was taken into account by normalizing to -25 per mil with respect to Pee Dee Belemnite (PDB), the postulated mean value of terrestrial wood, as we had yet not determined in our experiments the ^{14}C fractionation factor (i.e. $^{13}\text{C}/^{14}\text{C}$ ratio). The Neolithic era as a whole was characterized by the presence of a large number of objects made from bone and horn. The settlements of the Mugan Neolithic site possess the same characteristics. A large number of bone and, to a lesser extent, horn products with functional purposes have been discovered. Piercings predominate and are mostly made from small-bodied tubular bones. In most cases, longitudinally split bone was used for this purpose, with preservation or removal of the epiphytic head and sharpening of the other end. Less often, the end of the tubular bone was obliquely cut and sharpened. Along with tubular bone, there are also piercings from other bones. Knife-like hollows also prevail, made of longitudinally cut scapula.

Conference Programme

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Division of Geochronology and Environmental Isotopes

Institute of Physics – Centre for Science and Education

Silesian University of Technology

Konarskiego 22B, 44-100 Gliwice, Poland

What do we do?

Division of Geochronology and Environmental Isotopes is a unique scientific unit, where nineteen persons delve into the fundamentals of physical isotope methods and their applications. We are engaged in interdisciplinary research projects in Earth and environmental sciences, archaeology and history. We also offer expertise services for national and foreign institutions.

Two Laboratories are functioning within the Division:

1. Radiocarbon and Mass Spectrometry Laboratory

- Radiocarbon measurements with various techniques (LSC, AMS)
- Light stable isotope determinations (HCNO) with IRMS

2. Luminescence Dating Laboratory

- Dosimetric dating methods (OSL, TL)
- Radioisotope measurements (γ and α spectrometry, e.g. ^{137}Cs , ^{210}Pb)

Why do we do it?

The isotope methods find its applications to construct the calendar timescales for Earth and human history, for geology, geomorphology, palaeoclimatic research, palaeogeography. They also allow to trace natural environmental processes and human impact. Isotopes have proved to be invaluable tools for biological research, like palaeobotany or dendrology, for anthropology, archaeology and palaeozoology - e.g. for diet reconstructions.

What do we offer?

- Work with a team of specialist in various isotope methods
- Gain experience in multidisciplinary research
- Get involved in international cooperation

Contact person Head of the Division of Geochronology and Environmental Isotopes
Dr hab. eng. Natalia Piotrowska, prof. in SUT e-mail: natalia.piotrowska@polsl.pl

Monday 05 July 2021: **Methods**

9:30-10:10

Andrzej Rakowski

Opening

chair: Andrzej Rakowski

Session 1

10:10-10:50

Walter Kutschera (invited speaker)

The versatile uses of the ^{14}C bomb peak

10:50-11:30

Hans-Arno Synal (invited speaker)

Progress in AMS and Opportunities for Applications in Environment Research

11:30-11:50

coffee break

Session 2

chair: Irka Hajdas

11:50-12:10

Hangtao Shen

The ^{14}C -AMS technology and its applications for evaluation of the Properties of highly permeable aquifers cause by large volume water injection in oil field

12:10-12:30

Gianluca Quarta

The IAEA forensics program: results of the AMS ^{14}C inter-comparison exercise on contemporary wines and coffees

12:30-12:50

Konstantin Pustovoytov

^{14}C in biogenic carbonate of plant origin: environmental factors and potential for radiocarbon dating

12:50-13:10

Aybaniz Ahadova

Comparative Dating of Charcoal, Tooth and Ceramic Samples from the Polutepe Archeological Site in Azerbaijan

13:10-14:10

lunch break